

Synthesis of Some New Organoselenium Ligands

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ABSTRACT

Thirteen complex of new macrocycles ligands (which contain selenium Se_2N_4 type) were synthesized & Characterized by Elemental analysis, Molar conductance, IR, followed by XPS data.

Keyword: Organoselenium, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, Macrocylic complexes.

Introduction

The Element Selenium was discovered by JonsBerrzilius in 1818. Selenium show two types (II) and (IV) Valancies. Although Manyorganoselenium compound have been reported, organoselenium (II) compounds are comparatively less Known¹⁻⁹. The macrocycles containing heavier chalcogen are very few and mixed donor macrocycles containing selenium/ tellurium as donor are still rare. The complexation properties of homoleptic cyclic selenoethers such as [8]aneSe₂, [14]aneSe₄, [16]aneSe₄, [24]aneSe₆ with transition metal ions have been well studied¹⁰⁻¹³. The main group metal ions (III), Sb(III) and Bi(III) complexation properties with these selenoethers macrocycle have been also studied.¹⁴⁻¹⁷ The first mixed donor selenium macrocycle and its complexation properties with Ni and Cu¹⁸, the novel macrobicyclic cage incorporating N and Se as donor site and its complexation with Co(III)¹⁹. The first seleno crown ethers and its coordinates behaviours with metal ions²⁰ coordinate behaviours with metal ions²⁰ and heavy metal ions and other many selenoethers and its complexation behaviour with metal ions have been well studied.²¹⁻³⁷. The use of Selenium/tellurium based synthetic method is well established inorganic synthesis. Organoselenium /tellurium moieties can be incorporated into variety of substrate for functional under mild condition either as nucleophile or as electrophile. The coordination of heteroatom oxygen or nitrogen to the selenium leads to formation of heterocycle in a fixed conformation and increase the Stereoselectivity. Recently some mixed donor ligands containing Phosphorus as donor ligands also reported. Finally This chapter deals with synthesis of new Se_2N_4 selenium containing macrocylic ligands and their characterisation.

Synthesis of Selenium Containing Macrocylic Ligands

Preparation of selenium containing macrocylic Ligands(L¹ or L²,orL³,or L⁴,or L⁵ ,orL⁶ ,orL⁷,orL⁸ ,or L⁹,orL¹⁰ ,orL¹¹ ,or L¹² ,or L¹³):

2mmol of bis-benjaldehydeselenide in dry methanol was in 1 mmol in dry methanol of 2,6-diaminopyridine and in this mixture was poured into 1mmol of 1,5-carbohydrazine or 1,5-thiocarbohydrazine or 1,3-diamino-propane or 1,2-diamino propane or 2-2dimethyl 1,3-diaminopropane or diethylenetriamine or 1,6-diaminohexane or 1,7-diaminoheptane or 1,8-diaminooctaone or 1,9-diamino nonane or 1,10-diamino-decane or 1,12-diaminododecane dry methanol and refluxed for 3 hrs. The solid yellowish product was obtained filtered washed with dry methanol and air-dried (To get L²,orL³ ,orL⁴,orL⁵ orL⁶,orL⁷ ,orL⁸,orL⁹ ,orL¹⁰,orL¹¹ ,orL¹²,orL¹³ respectively. (Scheme1).

Experimental Process

Preparation of Selenium Containing macrocylic ligands

The preparation of the ligand is given below in (scheme 1) Orthotoluidine was used as starting materials. *o*-bromobenzaldehyde was prepared following the reported procedure³⁸. *n*-Butyllithium was added to *o*-bromobenzaldehyde acetal in ether at room temperature as reported by Piette and Renson and stirred for 15 minute to get *o*-lithiobenzaldehyde acetal as a cloudy white slurry subsequently, Se(dte)₂ was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for one hour at room temperature in case of se precursor. The reaction mixture was extracted with ether. On evaporation of solvent the compound was separated out. The deprotection of aldehyde group was performed by refluxing the acetal with concentrated HCl⁴⁰. This bisaldehyde was used as the precursor for the preparation of macrocycles using the reported procedure as given below. To a solution of 27.6 gm(0.1mol) of ethylene acetal of *o*-bromobenzaldehyde in 200 ml of ether at 15-20⁰C was added dropwise under stirring a solution of *n*-butyllithium obtained from 17.8 gm(0.13 ml) of *n*-butyl bromide and 2.1gm (0.3ml) of lithium in 250 ml of ether at -30⁰C. The mixture was allowed to warm till room temperature and added portionwise 19.1gm (0.05 ml) of Se(dtc)₂. The mixture was heated for 20-30 minute with stirring, cooled and poured over 500 ml of ice-water, filtered. The ether layer separated dried over CaCl₂ and ether was evaporated in air. The liberated *n*-butylbromide during the exchange reaction was removed under vacuum till all remaining solidified. 18 g(85%) yields of this product was obtained as yellow crystalline substance. Three times crystalline from a mixture of acetone-pentane (2:1) gave large colourless crystals. Then in a 250 ml three-neck flask equipped with condenser and stirring the above amount (18g) of bis-ethylene acetal of the bis-aldehyde selenide was dissolved in a mixture of solvent(25ml CCl₄±25 ml methanol). To this mixture 15 ml of 6N-HCl was added and mixture heated under vigorous stirring for one hr. 40ml of water was further refluxed under stirring for sometimes. The reaction mixture was transferred to a separately funnel, washed 2-3 times with water. The organic layer was separated and dried with little benzene azeotropically. The excess of CCl₄ was distilled off to reduce the volume upto 20 ml and the

product was precipitated by the addition of hexane and strong cooling .Bright yellow crystalline product with m.p 156(CCl₄) yield 12 g (95%).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The values of element analysis and molar conductance of all these prepared selenium containing macrocyclic ligands are listed in Table-1. They are soluble in organic solvents and stable at room temperature for a long time. Molar conductance of 10⁻³M solution of these ligands were determined at room temperature. The Molar conductance values range from 20-30 ohm⁻¹cm²mol⁻¹ in acetone suggesting non electrolyte nature of all these ligands. The IR spectra of L¹, or L², or L³, or L⁴, or L⁵, or L⁶, or L⁷, or L⁸, or L⁹, or L¹⁰, or L¹¹, or L¹², or L¹³, a band in the region 1620-1600cm⁻¹ due to C=O vibration. The bands at 230-260cm⁻¹ assigned to Se-C⁴¹. The binding energies (eV) data for N1s and Se3P1/2 photoelectron peaks have listed in Table 2 & 3. Se3P1/2 photoelectron peak in all these prepared ligands were observed. Symmetrical at BE ~ 168.8 eV (Table 2). On the basis of elemental analysis molar conductance, IR and XPS data, the possible structure of these all prepared monocyclic ligands

have been shown fig 1 to 21.

Table1-Analytical data of Ligands

Sr.no	Ligands	% Found calculated			Molarconductance in acetone ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹
		C	H	N	
1.	L ¹	67(67.2)	3.8(3.8)	7.4(7.6)	14
2	L ²	59.6(59.8)	3.6(3.7)	11.8(11.9)	16
3	L ³	58.2(58.4)	3.6(3.6)	11.4(11.6)	18
4	L ⁴	64.6(64.7)	4.2(4.3)	8.0(8.1)	20
5	L ⁵	65.0(65.1)	4.4(4.5)	8.0(8.0)	14
6.	L ⁶	65.4(65.5)	4.6(4.7)	7.6(7.8)	18
7.	L ⁷	63.6(63.7)	4.4(4.6)	9.6(9.7)	20
8	L ⁸	66.0(66)	4.6(4.8)	7.6(7.7)	14
9	L ⁹	66.2(66.3)	5.0(5.1)	7.4(7.5)	16
10	L ¹⁰	66.6(66.6)	5.0(5.1)	7.3(7.40)	17
11	L ¹¹	67.1(67.0)	5.4(5.4)	7.2(7.2)	20
12	L ¹²	67.2(67.3)	5.4(5.6)	7.0(7.1)	22
13.	L ¹³	68.0(68.0)	5.6(5.70)	6.8(6.9)	24

Table-2 Se₃P_{1/2} binding energy(ev) in ligands

Sr.no	Ligands	Se ³ P ^{1/2}
1.	L ¹	168.8
2.	L ²	168.8
3.	L ³	168.8
4.	L ⁴	168.8
5.	L ⁵	168.8
6.	L ⁶	168.8
7.	L ⁷	168.8
8.	L ⁸	168.8
9.	L ⁹	168.8
10.	L ¹⁰	168.8
11.	L ¹¹	168.8
12.	L ¹²	168.8
13.	L ¹³	168.8

Fig. 1 : Se3p_{1/2} binding energies (eV) in ligands

Conclusion:

Although many organoselenium (IV) compounds have been reported, organoselenium(II) compounds are comparatively less known. The macrocyclic containing heavier chalcogens are very few and mixed donor macrocycles containing selenium/tellurium as donor are still rare. Bis-salicylaldehydeselenide were synthesized as given in scheme 1¹⁰⁻¹¹ selenium containing macrocyclic ligands L¹ or L² or L³ or L⁴ or L⁵ or L⁶ or L⁷ were synthesized as given in or L⁸ or L⁹ or L¹⁰ or L¹¹ or L¹² or L¹³ were synthesized as given in (scheme 1). All these prepared selenium containing macrocyclic ligands i.e. L¹ to L¹³ were stable non-electrolyte and characterized by elemental analysis, molar conductivity, IR and XPS data and established their structure as shown in fig 1-fig 21. This Chapter deals with synthesis of twenty six other new selenium containing macrocyclic ligands and their characterisation. Bis-naphthaleneselenide was prepared as shown in (scheme 1). These all prepared selenium containing macrocyclic ligands were characterised by elemental analysis, molar conductance, IR and XPS and their structure was established as shown in fig (9-21).

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